

EVOLUTION OF TEACHER EDUCATION CURRICULUM IN PRE-INDEPENDENCE INDIA: A HISTORICAL PERSPECTIVE

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Abstract

Teaching is a noble profession in Indian culture. The teacher is an agent of social change and also a social engineer. According to Rabindranath, "A teacher can never truly teach unless he is still learning himself. A lamp can never light another lamp unless it continues to burn its flame". There are two main objectives of this study. They are first to identify the changes in the teacher education curriculum in India before independence, and second to identify the reasons behind the changes in the teacher education curriculum. The researcher has used a historical method for this study. The researcher has found out that before the British period, formal teacher education did not exist. During the British period, the first formal teacher training institution was established by the missionaries. Wood's Despatch was the first educational document that emphasized on teacher education. Before independence in India, many commissions, committees, and policies were recommended for the improvement of the teacher education curriculum. Researchers have identified that the teacher education curriculum has been changed over time due to commissions, committees, and policy recommendations.

Key Words: *Change, Teacher education, Curriculum.*

Introduction:

Gurur Brahma, Guru Vishnuh,

Gurur Devo Maheshwaraha,

Gurur Sakshat Parabrahma,

Tasmai Shri Gurave Namaha,

“Gu” means dark, and “Ru” means light. So, “Guru” can be roughly translated as darkness to light, or possibly as " one who leads from darkness to light. In Indian culture, the teacher is called the ‘Guru’. The ‘Guru’ is the second father. He teaches his disciples how to live properly in a society. In the Brahmanical education system, parents donate their son to a ‘Guru’ through ‘Upanayana’ rituals, and the Guru takes responsibility for their novice. The teaching profession is a noble profession in the Indian subcontinent from the Vedic period to the present day. In the ancient and medieval periods, formal teacher training institutions did not exist for teacher training, but formal teacher training found its roots in the Buddhist period. Teachers were trained for the purpose of propagating Buddhism. They were monks spreading the spirit of the Buddhist religion to the people. In the British period, the first formal training institution was established by the missionaries. Rabindranath Tagore said that “A teacher can never truly teach unless he is still learning himself. A lamp can never light another lamp unless it continues to burn its own flame”.

Objectives of the study:

- To discuss the historical development of teacher education in India before independence.
- To explore the significant shifts in teacher education between the ancient period, the Buddhist period, the Muslim period, and the British period.

Methodology:

This paper is based on the historical method. The researcher has used primary and secondary sources of data for data collection.

Discussion

Vedic-Brahmanic Education

The Vedic-Brahminic age of education is divided into three phases broadly based on social, religious, and political perspectives. They are Vedic phase, Post-Mourya, and Sunga era to the downfall of Kanouj. Formal pupilage begins with Upanayana and ends with Sambartana. Gurukul and Pathsala were the institutions of Brahmanic education. The subjects that were taught in Brahminic learning were the Vedas, the Brahmana, the Aranyaka, and the Vedanta. They also used to recite mantras in correct rhythm, pronunciation, and phonetic sound. They recited this mantra in meaningful understanding together with perfect rituals. This helped the development of six Vedangas- Siksha (phonetics), Chhanda (the science of rhyme and meter), Vyakarana (grammar), Nirukta (etymology), Jyotisha (astrology), and Kalpa (law and rituals). The complete Brahminic curriculum comprised of the three Vedas, six vedangas, Brahmana, *Copyright © 2025, Scholarly Research Journal for Interdisciplinary Studies*

Vedanta, Upanishads, Naya, Mimamsa, Vakovakyam (theological discourses), Itihasa-purana, Akhyan, Anvakhyan, Anuvakshyana (explanation), Vyakhyan (commentaries), Gatha, Kshatra vidya, Rasi (number), Nakshatra vidya (jyotish), Bhuta vidya (demonology), Magic, Science of life, Sarpa vidya, Daiva vidya, Nidhi, Sutra (sacrificial rituals), Ekayana (niti sastra), Brahma vidya (Vedanga-Devajana vidya), etc. forming a vast curriculum. Despite varied subjects, the teachers gave more importance to Para vidya because without Para vidya, everything was nothing but words (J. P. Banerjee, pp. 12-47). The teachers did not need any special professional training other than what they obtained through the monitorial system and public debates. They were required to be highly qualified and had an ideal character and patience. They also had to be impartial and have sound knowledge about the subject, and a lifelong study. For their professional skills, they delivered fluently with ready wit and the capacity to solve complicated problems instantly. They could inspire their pupils. Moreover, they had to follow an unwritten professional code. They did not accept any regular fees. They had to share with their pupils all their knowledge and confess their deficiencies. So, they were worshiped with much admiration.

In non-commercial teachership, a teacher had the inherent right to absolute control of the institution. It included admission, removal, and punishment. The teachers had the authority to determine the curriculum, syllabus, and teaching methods. The teacher was the only examiner and evaluator of the student's competency.

Buddhistic Education (500 B.C. to 1200 A.D.)

The Buddhist education system first began with the education for monks, but with the sacred task of serving others, there gradually needed to be a practical education. When religion entered the masses, a mass education was also required. Therefore, the Buddhist education system was built in three phases: monk education, home education, and mass education. Sutra Pitak, Dharma Pitak, and Vinaya Pitak were the three compulsory subjects for monks in higher education. Because of the co-existence with Brahminic education, the Buddhist scholars also needed to be experts in Brahminic educational knowledge. Some contents of Brahminic education were also included in Buddhist education. 'Milinda Panho' shows the extension of the curriculum of the Buddhist education system. It informs Vedas, Itihasa(history), Purana, Chanda, Kavya, Vyakarana (grammar), Jyotisha (astrology), etc., which were also gradually included in the curriculum. For debate and philosophical thoughts, Sankha, Yoga, Naya, and Vaisheshika were also taught. Also, for the practical purpose, Mathematics, Medical, Music, Magic, etc., were included in the curriculum. From the tales of Jataka, it is known that there is

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also freedom in the selection of various subjects in the curriculum. In accordance with that, multiple universities were also set up. Different schools were also found in Taxila, and besides the three Vedas and Buddhist scriptures, science, Arts, and architecture were also studied.

Unlike the Brahmin education system, it is not that people from one Varna (caste) had the right to teach. Still, in the Buddhist education system, any person with vigorous training could become a teacher. A formal system of teacher training had emerged in the Buddhist education system.

A person who possessed moral behavior, inherent cognition, belief in Nirvana, kindness, was free from all ties of the world, and was afraid to commit any sin, would be able to teach. There were two types of teachers in Buddha Bihar: The teacher of ‘Dharma Tattva’ is called ‘Upacharya’, and the teacher of moral lessons is called ‘Acharya’ or ‘Karmacharya’.

Islamic Period (1200 A.D to 1700 A.D.)

Although three types of schools existed in the Islamic education system in India, there was no formal system of training. (Shashi Prabha Sharma, p.14). Maktabas were primary educational institutions, and Madrasas were higher educational institutions. Maulavi was the teacher of these institutions. The curriculum of maktab was mainly 3Rs (reading, writing, and arithmetic) and parts of the Quran (J. P. Banerjee, p.139). The subjects of Madrasas were not uniform, and students of different Madrasas could choose different subjects. Badani classified the subjects into two groups in higher education. They were Sciences (intellectual), viz. philosophy, geometry, mechanics, astronomy, arithmetic, and other subjects requiring memory work. Abul Fazl classified the subjects under three heads in higher education: Ilahi, dealing with divine sciences and theology; Riyazi, dealing with mathematics, astronomy, music, and medicine; and Tabiqi, dealing with all physical sciences.

A characteristic of medieval Islamic education was that it depended on the personal character of the king. If the king was educated or a scholar, then he would have taken enough care to spread education in the empire. Akbar was a lover of teaching, and education underwent a radical change during his reign. Abul Fazl gave an account of Akbar's instructions on education in *Ain-e Akbari*. Akbar ordered that students first learn the Persian alphabet and pronunciation, and where to place the punctuation marks. If these are learned in a few days, then the alphabet will be learned. After a week, they will try to read small morals or poetry and prose works about religion. Students will try to proceed as independently as possible. The teachers would help the students as little as possible. The teacher would observe some aspects, like alphabet, word meaning, compound words, sloke (couplet), and their memorization.

In the Islamic education system, there was no such professional training to become a teacher. The teacher was selected based on their academic qualifications. Only the Muslims were eligible to teach in *Mokhatab* and *Madrasah* (Shashi Prabha Sharma, P. 14). In the Buddhist period, trained person was engaged in the teaching profession, and this teacher education was not only based on religious education; it was focused on life skills, but Islamic education was based on religious education. The Moulavi dominated the teaching profession. The institutions of Buddhist education were *Behar* and *Songha*, and it was separated from the local area, but the institution of Islamic education was *Masjid* centric. The Buddhist teacher training system was semi-formal, but Islamic education was informal, and there was no special institution or curriculum for teacher education.

British period (1700 A.D to 1947 A.D.)

The Britishers changed the Indian education system according to their philosophical approach. They did not recognize the monitorial system of teaching and the semiformal system of teacher training as the teacher training system. Their main objective was that Indian children would be educated according to the British education system. The Britishers started a formal system of teacher education. The first formal teacher training school was established at *Serampur* in *Bengal* in 1793 by *Carey*, *Marsh*, and *Ward*. It was the collaborative effort of *Danish* and *English* missionaries. The first educational despatch was *Wood's Despatch*. This Despatch emphasized teacher training; they recommended that the defects, such as an insufficient number of qualified school masters, the imperfect method of teaching, be found out, and for remedy, regular schools were established in *England*. Similarly, in *India*, regular schools would be established in each presidency to modify those defects. As for the admission in *Medical* and *Engineering* college, which was maintained by the state, admission in the

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Normal school would be maintained by the state. They emphasized that the teacher would be competent with the new teaching and the best evaluation method. The teaching profession did not depend on a person's caste, creed, or religion, but it depended on the competency of the teaching profession. Hunter Commission (1882) noticed that every presidency had a different teacher training curriculum. They opined that the curriculum should be taken in one permanent system. The Normal school emphasized the science and practice of teaching. The teacher would have to know the principles and methods of teaching through training. The commission told about evaluation "That an examination in the principles and practice of teaching be instituted, success in which should thereafter be a condition of permanent employment as a teacher in any secondary school, Government or aided". (Nurulla Nayek, p.200). Education Policy-1904 emphasized teacher training in those presidencies where there were no teacher training institutions; a training institution would be adopted there. The trained teacher would be supplied to every secondary school in India through the extension of training institutions. With this, not only would the number of qualified teachers increase, but also the quality of education would be improved. The duration of teachers' training for graduate teachers would be one year, and for others, the duration would be two years. The training college would be well equipped with a sound library, a museum, and trained teachers. Calcutta University Commission (1917) first recommended the establishment of a unitary teaching university in India. They mentioned the establishment of the education department and also provided B.A. and M.A. degrees. They stressed on the practice teaching in the teacher training curriculum. They recommended that a small experimental school would be engaged in a large practicing school, and by this, the pupil teacher would get an opportunity in an educational experiment. Hartog Committee (1929) suggested that about teacher education, "The training of the teacher is infinitely more important than the mere alteration of the curriculum. The same curriculum can, for example, be interpreted in entirely different ways by two teachers who have not received similar training. A teacher trained to have what may be called a rural bias will make knowledge a living thing in relation to everyday happenings in village life. In contrast, a teacher without rural bias will probably never be able to make his pupils appreciate that the acquisition of knowledge has some relation to actual life" (Indian Statutory Commission-1929, p.63). Post World War II report gave importance to teacher training and suggested that in teachers' training, not only the requisite professional training would be provided, but also, in this way, they would be taught so that more young boys and girls would like to join this profession. They recommended a two-

year teacher training course for pre-primary teachers, junior basic, and non-graduate teachers. Senior basic teacher training should be one year.

Islamic education was based on religion-centric principles, but British education was secular. Informal teacher training of Islamic education was teacher-centric, but in the British period, teacher training institutions were student-centric, and the curriculum was based on pedagogy, philosophy, and psychology.

Significant shift in teacher education:

Determination	Ancient period	Buddhist period	Islamic period	British period
Focus	Religion education	Religion education	Religion education	Secular education
Teaching profession	Dominated by Brahmin	Not dominated by any Caste or Varna	Dominated by Moulavi	Formally trained person
Forms of training	Informal	Semiformal	Informal	Formal
Institution	Gurukul, Ashram	Bihar, Sangha	Maktab, Madrasah	Normal school
Curriculum	Vedas, philosophy, ethics, and physical training	Moral education, ethics, Tri Pitak,	Quran, Hadith, Arabic, philosophy, religious guidance,	Pedagogy, psychology, teaching method, practicum, practice teaching
Teaching method	Observation, imitation, spiritual discussion	Discussion, dialogue, reasoning	Memorization, rote learning	Lecture method, observation, and active participation learning

Conclusion

In the Brahmanic period, the teachers did not need any special professional training other than what they obtained through the monitorial system and public debates. They are required to be highly qualified, ideal characters, and patient. They also had to be impersonal and sound knowledgeable about the subject and lifelong study. In Buddhist education, any person with vigorous training could become a teacher. A formal system of teacher training had emerged in the Buddhist education system. A person who possessed moral behavior, inherent cognition, belief in nirvana, kindness, was free from all ties of the world, and was afraid to commit any kind of sin, would be able to teach appropriately. In the Islamic education system, there was no such professional training to become a teacher. The teacher was selected based on their academic qualifications. Only the Muslims were eligible to teach in mokalis and madrasahs. During the British period, the first formal teacher training institution was established. In

Madras, the government-regular school was established in 1856. During the British period, various commissions and committees recommended improvements to teacher training. Secular teacher training education was started, and any trained person could join this profession.

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